

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese

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Abstract

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This study aimed to analyze type I and its subtypes' characteristics of Balinese noun lexemes meaning categories. The theory used was Semantic Theory. It applied qualitative research with the data obtained from written and spoken data. The data were collected through observation and interview methods. It is then analyzed using the distributional methods. Meanwhile, the analysis was presented in formal and informal methods. The results of the study are as follows. Type I was characterized by the main meaning [+thing +person(O)], and its additional characteristics; [Object, +(ND), +(Ny), +(K), -uncountable (-H)]. Furthermore, I subtype was divided into 6 subtypes, i.e.: IA subtype: [+B,+ O, +ND, +Ny, +K, +-h]; IB subtype: [+B, +O, +NK, +Ny, +K, +-h]; IC subtype:[+B, +O ,+NP, +Ny, +K, +-h]; ID subtype: [+B, +O, +NJ, Ny, +K, +-h]; IE subtype:[+B, +O, +ND, +Ny, +K, +-h]; IF subtype: [+B, +O, +ND, +Ny, + K, +-h].

1. Introduction

The Balinese language is one of the regional languages still alive and developing (Aryawibawa et al., 2018). With the progress of the era, it is feared that the Balinese language is believed be spoken less (Cf. Dewi et al., 2022; Candrawati et al., 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to strive to preserve and develop the Balinese language to minor aspects so that all aspects of the Balinese language are inventoried (Cf. Sujaya et al., 2021). Until now, many studies have been conducted on the Balinese language. The research includes microlinguistics, macro linguistics, and applied linguistics. However, this does not mean that there is no problem with the Balinese language that needs further investigation. However, many Balinese language problems need to be investigated again because the

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Balinese language is very rich in linguistic repertoire. One of the areas that is rarely studied is the problem of semantics, especially the category of lexical meaning.

In grammatical studies, word categories can never be separated from the conversation. Looking at grammar books, it is found that only some people talk about word categories. However, there is almost no agreement among linguists because the category of lexical meaning is so essential, complicated, and complex (Cf. Hartmann & Stork, 1972; Cassani et al., 2020; Krismayani et al., 2020; Mahardika et al., 2021). Generally, the most followed grammatical categories divide words into two major groups (1) a group called the whole word and (2) a group called particle or task word.

The first group consists of words: verbal, nominal, adjective, and adverbial, while the second group consists of words called prepositions, conjunctions, and interjections. However, basic morphemes still need to be categorized, both grammatically or semantically (Chaer, 1990, p. 147; Hartmann & Stork, 1972; Gao et al., 2022). It means that the category of lexical meaning is comprehensive and impossible to work on at once. In addition, grammatical categories in Balinese must be investigated so that they can be inventoried and preserved before they begin to disappear as Indonesian or other languages influence them. One of the categories of lexical meaning, namely the category of noun lexical meaning in Balinese.

This research is research in the field of semantics which is a part of micro linguistics, explicitly discussing the categories of the lexical meaning of nouns in Balinese. This research is vital since the types of the lexical meaning of nouns in each language are different. It is because the socio-cultural background of the people who speak each language differs. Especially the Balinese language, which has speakers of very varied cultural backgrounds; of course, it has a higher number of meanings in the noun lexicon when compared to Indonesian.

Considering the broad and many types and subtypes of categories of meaning in the noun lexicon in Balinese, on the current research, only one type is discussed, namely type A and its subtypes. Therefore, this research must be carried out and published in the article. Thus, there are two problems discussed in this article, namely (1) What sub-types of meaning categories of noun lexemes are found in Balinese? and (2) What are the characteristics of each subtype of the meaning category of Balinese noun lexicon? Moreover, it formulates the characteristics of each subtype category and the meaning of the type I noun lexicon in Balinese. With the achievement of these two objectives, the contents of this article can be helpful to various parties in developing semantic theory, especially the category of lexicon meaning.

2. Materials and Methods

This research uses the library method and field method. The library method is done by listening to a collection of Balinese stories. Oral data were obtained from native Balinese speakers in Bali. Researchers went into the field to obtain data on Balinese speakers. This method can be further elaborated into the listening and speaking methods (especially face-to-face) (Sudaryanto, 1993: 2-9; Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Malterud (2001) refers to observation for the listening method and the interview for the proficient method (capable of face-to-face).

The listening method is done by listening to the Pupulan Satua Bali Book. In addition, the researchers also listen to Balinese speakers whom the speaker does not know. Because listening to the script, the technique needed is only a note-taking technique. The proficient method is carried out by conducting interviews with predetermined informants. This speaking method uses the fishing technique as the primary technique. The advanced speaking method is a face-to-face conversation technique carried out by direct/face-to-face conversation.

Data Analysis Methods and Techniques

Qualitative methods are used because this research reveals research not using numbers (O'Connor & Joffe, 2020). In the data analysis stage, this research uses the distributional method (Sudaryanto, 1993, pp. 13-30; Garvin, 2019, p. 58; and Richards & Rodgers, 2014). The linguistics field method is assisted by basic and advanced techniques applied to the data studied (Sudaryanto (1993: 31-100). The basic technique is very relevant to the initial discussion of the Category of Nominal lexical meaning in Balinese. The follow-up technique consists of substitution and expansion techniques, which can be used to test whether the word category is nominal. Formal and informal methods present data analysis with deductive techniques.

The theory applied in this research is the Semantic theory of Chaer (1990). In general, linguistics's semantics refers to the part of linguistics that studies meaning. It investigates meaning in language and is one of three levels of language analysis, namely phonology, grammar, and semantics (Frawley, 2013; Hartmann & Stork, 1972; Garvin, 2019). There is a discussion about the Category of Lexical Meaning. The category of lexical meaning is inclusive, as explained in the introduction. The part used in this study follows the title, namely the category of the lexical meaning of the noun.

Chaer (1990) explains that noun lexemes in Indonesian semantically contain the meaning of [+noun (b)] and, therefore, structurally nominal lexemes can always be preceded by prepositions 'at.' Based on further semantic analysis, nominal lexemes in Indonesian are grouped into ten types and several subtypes. In the current research, only one type is presented: type A and its subtypes.

3. Results and Discussions

In accordance with the problems in the introduction, two problems are discussed in the current research. However, the two problems cannot be discussed separately because of the types and subtypes of the meaning of the nominal lexical category of speech and their characteristics. The following categories of the lexical meaning of nouns in Balinese are presented in more detail. In Balinese, there are 12 types of noun lexical meaning categories, and each type has subtypes. According to the previous discussion, only type I and its subtypes will be discussed in the current research. For more details, the following is a description based on data in Balinese.

Category I Lexical Meaning of Balinese Nouns and Subtypes and Their Characteristics

Category I lexical meaning has the main characteristic [+ thing + person (O)]. This type has 6 subtypes, each of which differs in the third meaning feature. In Balinese, some subtypes have more characteristics than those in Indonesian. The six subtypes are as follows. The category of lexical meaning of subtype IA is characterized by [+B, + O ,+ Name (ND), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

The IA subtype in Balinese can also still be grouped because the Balinese self-name is strongly influenced by the *wangsa* system. Each dynasty, wears a different personal name that is located at the beginning of its name. The *wangsa* system in Bali can be divided into two, namely the *Triwangsa* which consists of the *Brahmana*, *Ksatria*, and *wesya*; and non-*Triwangsa* often called *jaba*. The four of them have the characteristic of self-naming at the beginning. Gender also affects the name of each of these dynasties. In addition to *wangsa* and gender, birth order also affects the Balinese self-name.

For birth order not all dynasties use, but in general, birth order matters. The first birth order is used by *Gede*, *Wayan*, *Putu* (male and female) and even *Cening* (female only); the second birth order is used by *Made*, *Kadek*, and *Nengah* (male and female); for birth order number three there are

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese
(NM Suryati, IW Suteja, IK Jirnaya)

Komang and *Nyoman* (male and female); and birth order number four is *Ketut* (male girl). If there are more than four births it will return to multiples. To find out more detailed self-names in Balinese, it can be explained in each *wangsa*. Next, based on the data, it was found that the nominal lexical meaning category in Balinese subtype IA has the following characteristics;

a) *Brahmana Buda*: [+B, + O ,+ Personal Name (*Ida*+rank name (which you like)+name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (- H).

Example: *Ida Made Oka*

Ida Wayan Oka

Ida Made Siwi

b) *Brahmana Male Shiva*: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Ida Bagus* + birth order(whichever)+ name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H) .

Example: *Ida Bagus Nyoman Subali*

Ida Bagus Putu Adnyana

Ida Bagus Manuaba

Ida Bagus Ari Suta

c) *Brahmana Shiva Woman*: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Ida Ayu*+birth order (whichever you like)+ name),+ life (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *Ida Ayu Putu Mahuni*

Ida Ayu Made Suastini

Ida Ayu Laksmi Sari

Ida Ayu Rusmiati

d) *Male Knight*: [+B,+O,+ Personal Name (*Anak Agung* +birth order (which is like+name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *Anak Agung Gede Bawa*

Anak Agung Putu Putra

Anak Agung Putra Semadi

Anak Agung Oka

e) *Male Knight*: [+B, +O ,+ Name (*Cokorde*+ birth order (whichever)+ name), +animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K), -uncountable(-H).

Example: *Cokorde Gde Pemayun*

Cokorde Gde Darma Yuda

Cokorde Raka Sukawati

Cokorde Rai Sudharta

f) *Female Knight*: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Anak Agung Ayu*: birth order (whichever you like) + name), + life (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H)

Example: *Anak Agung Ayu Sulistyawati*

Anak Agung Ayu Candra Dewi

Anak Agung Ayu Putri Astiti

Anak Agung Ayu Candra Lestari

g) *Female Knight*: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Cokorde Wife* +birth order (whichever you like) +name),+ animate (Mrs),+ Concrete (K), -uncountable (-H)

Example: *Cokorde Istri Agung Mulyawati*
Cokorde Putra Hadriyani,
Cokorde Iatri Sukrawati

h) *Wesia* Male: [+B, + O ,+ Name (I Gusti +Lanang /Alit /Ngurah/Bagus+birth order (whichever you like)+name),+life (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *I Gusti Lanang Subamia I Gusti Ngurah Arya Widiantara*
I Gusti Alit
I Gusti Bagus Ravindra Kalyana

i) *Wesia* Male: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Ngakan* + birth order(whichever)+ name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *Ngakan Made Suparti*
Ngakan Putu Gede Suardana
Ngakan Pande Saputra
Ngakan Gde Suyasa

j) *Wesia* Female: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*I Gusti Ayu* + birth order (whichever you like) + name), + life (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H),

Example: *I Gusti Agung Ayu Pradnya Siwi*
I Gusti Ayu Milisari
I Gusti Ayu Gede Sosiowati
I Gusti Ayu Mardiani

k) *Wesia* Female: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*Sang Ayu* + birth order (whichever you like) + name), + life (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani*
Sang Ayu Tia
Sang Ayu Nela Siwi
Sang Ayu Sulistiwaty

l) Non *Triwangsa* Male: [+B, + O ,+ Name (*I* + Birth order (whichever you like) + name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H) .

Example: *I Wayan Sujana*
I Nyoman Suryawan
Putu Mita Darashana Viragita
Komang Paramartha

m) Non *Triwangsa* Female: [+B, + O ,+ Personal Name (*Ni*+ birth order (whichever)+ name), + animate (Mrs), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H).

Example: *Ni Made Suryati*
Made Sri Satyawati
Ni Wayan Arsyastini

Based on the presented data above, the nominal lexical meaning category in Balinese Subtype IA has 13 more special characteristics as mentioned above.

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese Subtype IB and Its Characteristics

The lexical meaning category of Balinese nouns subtype IB is characterized by: [+B, + O ,+ Kinship name (NK), + animate (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H)]. For this type, the Balinese language has many lexicon because the Balinese language recognizes language levels. In general, the Balinese language is divided into: *Balinese Alus* (BBA), *Balinese Madia* (BBM), *Balinese Kepara/Lumrah/Andap* (BBK/BBL/BBA, and Balinese Rough (BBKa) (Naryana, 1984: 21) so that sometimes an English word has 3 lexicals in Balinese, for example for the Balinese equivalent of the word Father: [ajik] for Balinese *alus* [bapə] for ordinary Balinese, and [nanan] for Balinese rather rude; for the word mother: [bian] (BBA), [ibu/meme] BBK.

Other kinship words are: *adi/ari* 'younger sister', *mbok* 'older sister', *b'li* 'older brother' (BBK) *misan* 'cousin', *mingsiki* (BBA) 'mindon cousin' / 'relationship between cousin's son and cousin's son', *mingtelu/ mimgtiga* 'cousin' relationship with cousin's grandson', *ipah/ipen* 'in-law' son-in-law' son-in-law', *matua* 'in-law' 'grandson', *ninik/niang* 'grandmother', *kaki/wayah/senak/kakiang* 'grandfather', *warang* 'besan', *meme kualon* 'stepmother', *rerama* 'uncle', *tante* 'aunt', *madu* 'honey', Differences in terms kinship is very influenced by the dynasty system. Based on the description above, the nominal lexical meaning categories in Balinese which are included in Type IB can be distinguished into the following characteristics.

1) Family name in tri with the following characteristics: [+B, + O ,+ Family name (NK) tri *wangsa*, + Animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H).

Example: - *Biang* 'mother'

- *Aji* 'Father'

- *Niang* 'grandmother'

- *Kakiang* 'grandfather'

- *Oka* 'child'

- *Rabbi* 'Wife'

- *Ming siki* 'cousin'

- *Ming kalih* 'relationship between cousins and cousins';

- *Semeton* 'brother'

- *Putu* 'grandson'

2) Non-*Triwangsa* kinship name, with characteristics: [+B, + O ,+ Kinship name (NK) non *triwangsa* + Animate (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H).

Example: *meme* 'mom'

bapa 'father'

panak/nak cerik 'child'

wayah/kaki/ pekak 'grandpa'

Nini, dadong, mbah, cucu 'grandma'

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese Subtype IC and Its Characteristics

The category of nominal lexical meaning in Balinese subtype IC is characterized by: [+B, + O ,+ Substitute Name (NP), + Animate (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H)]. In Indonesian (in which Balinese has interact with) or English, there are additional meanings (+singular) and (-singular). For example: *him* and *them*. In Balinese, there are no (+singular) and (-singular) forms, but there are *Alus* (A), *Madia* (M), *Andap/kepara/normal* (L), and Rude (K) so that this subtype can be characterized by

[+B, + O ,+ Surname (NP) (A/M/L/K), + animate (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H). The IC subtype lexicon can be characterized as following.

(1) [+B, + O ,+ Surname (NP) (A), + animate (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H)

Such as: *titiang* 'I',
Ida/dane/ipun 'S/he'
ragane 'you'.

(2) [+B, + O ,+ Surname (NP) (M), + Life (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H),

Such as: *tiang* 'I'
ragane 'You'

(3) [+B, + O ,+ Surname (NP) (L), + Life (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H),

Such as: - *cai* 'you (for male)',
 - *nyai* 'you (for female),
 - *icang* 'I'
 - *ia* 'S/he'

(4) [+B, + O ,+ Surname (NP) (K), + Life (Ny), + concrete (K) , - uncountable (+H),

Such as: *ake* 'I',
nani/iba 'you'.

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese Subtype ID and Its Characteristics

The category of lexical meaning of ID subtype nouns is characterized by [+B, + O ,+ Position Name (NJ), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , counted (+H). In Balinese language, it can still be divided into traditional position names (NJT) and modern positions (NJM). Thus this subtype can be divided into 2 characteristics, as follows.

1) Characteristics [+B, + O ,+ Title (NJ), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , - uncountable (-H) +Traditional.

Example:

- *Jero Pasek,*
- *Jero Nyarikan*
- *Jero kabayan*
- *Jero bau*
- *Juru batek*
- *Juru raksa*

(2) Characteristics: [+B, + O ,+ Name of Position (NJ), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , counted (+H)+M (Modern).

In fact, the modern name of the position, if discussed in detail, is very broad and can be made up of several characteristics. However, on this section only exemplified the names of positions in general. For example President, Vice President, Minister, Governor, Regent, *Perbekel*/Village Head, *Kliang*/Head of hamlet, Chancellor, Dean, Deputy dean, Study program coordinator, etc.

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese Subtype IE and Its Characteristics

The lexical meaning category of IE subtype nouns is characterized by [+B, + O ,+ Title Name (NG), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , counted (+H). The name of the title in Balinese is of course an absorption element because the title is generally accepted and also applies to regional languages. The blood languages of course have no special or original title names. Thus, the meaning of this IE subtype lexicon category is the same as that found in Indonesian language, namely, Doctor, Masters, Bachelor of Law, Bachelor of Economics, Bachelor of Animal Husbandry, Bachelor of Literature/Humanities, Bachelor of Mathematics, etc.

Category of Noun Lexical Meaning in Balinese Subtype IF and Its Characteristics

The category of lexical meaning of IF subtypes is characterized by [+B, + O ,+ Rank Name (NP), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K) , counted (+H). Names of rank in Balinese in particular also do not exist. Rank names are also taken from the Indonesian language. The examples of rank names are 'General' or 'Expert Assistant'.

4. Conclusion

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the types and subtypes along with the characteristics of the categories of meanings of the Balinese noun lexicon are as follows. Type I is characterized by the main meaning [+ thing + person (O)]. Additional features: [Item + Personal Name (ND), + animate (Ny), + Concrete (K), - uncountable (-H). Type I has 6 subtypes. The subtypes and characteristics of each subtype are as follows.

- Subtype IA characteristic: [+B, +O ,+ND, +Ny + K +-h]
- Subtype IB characteristic: [+B, +O ,+NK, +Ny + K +-h]
- Subtype IC characteristic: [+B, + O ,+ NP, +Ny + K +-h]
- Subtype ID characteristic: [+B, +O ,+NJ, +Ny + K +-h]
- Subtype IE characteristic: [+B, +O ,+ND, +Ny + K +-h]
- Subtype IF characteristic: [+B, +O ,+ND, +Ny + K +-h]

Next, research related to the lexical meaning category of the Balinese language is fundamental to be further studied since the meanings in the Balinese lexical category differ from other languages. It is suggested that the future researcher may conducting research in Balinese so that it can be used for comparative linguistic research of the archipelago.

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